

Parkinson's UK

Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	https://www.parkinsons.org.uk/sites/default/files/2017-06/Data%20sharing%20policy%20and%20guidelines%20May%202017.pdf
Definition of data	Final research data, basic research, clinical studies, surveys and other types of research. In particular, unique data that cannot readily be replicated or to projects that transform or link pre-existing datasets.
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Appropriate metadata to identify existing datasets and communal methodology and standards for the dataset. Consideration of legal, ethical, institutional and commercial restraints on data sharing No specification for data sharing plan
Required data repository	No specification for data sharing plan (but could use Critical Path for Parkinsons) or data enclave for sensitive information.
Time for data release	Timely and responsible, with limited period of exclusive use. Data should be made available once published
Time for long-term storage of data	Minimum period of 5 years following end of research grant.
Costings	Archiving, repository fees, data storage costs and data management services. Data management and sharing costs must be reasonable and proportionate in the context of the overall grant. Data sharing costs do not include open access publication costs.
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	researchapplications@parkinsons.org.uk
Comments	Data sharing plan will be reviewed as part of the funding decision.

Documents used:

Parkinson's Data sharing and preservation: Policy and guidelines

<https://www.parkinsons.org.uk/sites/default/files/2017-06/Data%20sharing%20policy%20and%20guidelines%20May%202017.pdf>

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